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**QUALITATIVE RESEARCH INTO THE PROS AND CONS OF BEING A
WOMAN ENTREPRENEUR IN THE NON-PROFIT SECTORS IN TURKEY**

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Özet

Sosyal girişimci kadınlar, karşılaştıkları sorunlar karşısında sessiz kalmak yerine hareket geçmeyi tercih eden ve girişimcilik ve yenilikçilik özellikleri ile sosyal etki yaratacak girişimler kurarak toplumlara sosyal etki anlamında önemli katma değer sağlayan kadınlardır. Bilindiği gibi küreselleşme ile birlikte dünya genelindeki kaynakların kullanımının eşitlenmesi yerine kaynak kullanımındaki adaletsizliğin arttığı görülmektedir. Günümüzde eşitsizlikler ortadan kalkacağına “aşağıdakiler” ve “yukarıdakiler” arasındaki makas iyice açılıyor. Sosyal sorunlara sadece hayırseverlik veya eğitim perspektifinden yaklaşan müdahaleler büyük resmi görmeyen, sorunları çözeceğine öteleyen yara bandı çözümler olmaktan öteye geçemiyor. Bu noktada, sosyal girişimciler kadın olma özelliklerini de kattıkları girişimcilik süreçlerinde, sistematik sorunlara çözüm aramak ve sosyal anlamda katma değer yaratmak amacı ile girişimcilik süreçlerini sürdürmektedirler.

Anahtar Kelimeler: Sosyal Girişimcilik, Kadın Girişimcilik, Girişimcilik

Abstract

Social entrepreneurial women are women who take action instead of being silent in the face of the problems they face and provide significant added value in terms of social impact, which they do by establishing initiatives that create social impact through entrepreneurship and innovation. As is known, inequality in resource use is increasing, not equalizing, worldwide. Today, instead of eliminating inequalities, the gap between the “following” and the “above” is being opened. Interventions that approach social problems from a philanthropic or educational perspective cannot go beyond being a band-aid solution which does not take the big picture into account. Here, social entrepreneurs continue their entrepreneurship processes with the aim of seeking solutions to systematic problems and creating added social value in the entrepreneurship processes, which in this case include the characteristics of being a woman.

Keywords: Social Entrepreneurship, Women Entrepreneurship, Entrepreneurship

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Introduction

Seen as a means of solving social problems, social entrepreneurship is increasing throughout the world as well as in Turkey. It is a problem-solving approach which is currently ascendant due to the increasing number of social problems and the insufficiency of the public to meet these social needs. Rather than addressing social problems one by one, social entrepreneurship aims to create fundamental and continuous change and to dissolve problems over the long term by spreading this change. For this reason, social entrepreneurship is seen as a tool of change and development.

The purpose of studying the pros and cons of women entrepreneurship especially in the non-profit sector is to support growth-oriented women's business, and to shed light on such women's perceptions of what it takes to be successful. Mainly, we endeavor to determine how the main internal and external influencers such as self-confidence, inner motivation, family support, enabling factors, and triggering events affect entrepreneurship as well as contribute to being an entrepreneur in the male-oriented business environment. Four research questions are constituted. They are;

RQ 1: What are the driving factors towards being a social entrepreneur?

RQ 2: How do women perceive their success in the field of social entrepreneurship in terms of the challenges of being a woman?

RQ 3: What helps to build up sustainable social relations regardless of the challenges encountered on the entrepreneurial path?

RQ 4: What are the obstacles in achieving your goal while working on solution-oriented social projects?

In the scope of the data obtained in light of these research questions, with regard to women entrepreneurs in the nonprofit sectors in Turkey, it will be possible to identify

the factors that push women into entrepreneurship, assess the difficulties that women face in social entrepreneurship processes, and evaluate their solution-oriented approaches in the context of social projects in terms of achieving their goals and objectives. These analysis findings cover the challenges faced by women social entrepreneurs in Turkey and determine solutions for coping with these challenges.

Social entrepreneurship is defined as non-profit, sustainable, innovative, and social value creating activities that can operate within the commercial and public sectors. The most important feature that distinguishes social enterprises from other charitable or commercial activities is that such activity creates sustainable social impact by recognizing innovative opportunities and applying innovative solutions. Social initiatives are created by social entrepreneurs to solve social problems and make the necessary impact for social development. In this study, the pros and cons of being a woman in social entrepreneurship are evaluated.

1. Social Entrepreneurship: Current Scheme and Components

The concept of social entrepreneurship is a type of entrepreneurship that aims to melt the concepts of “social” and “enterprise” in a pot. The contributions to be provided to the concept of entrepreneurship with the term “social” are as follows (Güler, 2008);

- Having social outcomes: Social entrepreneurship is expected to have a social impact as a result of its aim. It can also be described as offering innovative solutions to increasing social problems. Examples include increased employment, reduced unemployment, and reduced environmental issues.
- Consideration of social capital: There must be cooperation, trust, and connection between individuals and enterprises, and all of these should be seen as an element of financial and physical capital.
- Establishment of a social service organization: The aim and mission of the initiatives should be on behalf of the society and should create social value.
- Social entrepreneurs are also community entrepreneurs: Social entrepreneurs should form the basis of social development by focusing on solving community problems.

In today's global world, social entrepreneurship does have a complex structure. Social entrepreneurs bring about social change in the social sector. Social initiatives provide innovative solutions for creating social value and solving social problems. According to this premise, social entrepreneurship has the below characteristics;

- Having a mission that creates sustainable social value,
- Exploring and uncovering new opportunities in line with social missions,
- Participating in a continuous innovative and learning process,
- Exhibiting courage to create new things with available resources,
- Possessing an endless sense of responsibility in finding help and resources.

The components of social entrepreneurship are: social mission, social value/social impact, the opportunities for social enterprise, innovation, being sustainable, creating new resources, and using social networks.

The social mission of social enterprises enables them to address these problems from a wider perspective. Even if they start relatively small, the subsequent imitation and sustainability of social initiatives over larger dimensions will cause change. Having a social mission also affects the way people deal with problems and affects the perception and evaluation of opportunities (Dees, 1998).

The common point among all definitions of social entrepreneurship is that they create *social value*. The measure of the social value created by entrepreneurs is called social impact, not profit or customer satisfaction as the value created in commercial entrepreneurship is understood. Social initiatives can react differently to environmental and social events. In addition to focusing on social problems, social enterprises use different resources by creating innovative opportunities. By creating new social agreements, social entrepreneurs create resources from their own personal resources and the relationships that entrepreneurs have. Through donations, member dues, government support, project revenues, sponsorships, international funds, as well as social enterprises are creating value with different competitive opportunities by turning to commercial activities.

2. Women Entrepreneurship

In the literature, it is seen that a number of theoretical issues are examined in the studies on women entrepreneurs. In particular, when some studies are examined, it is remarkable that the enterprises owned by women are as successful as these women are (Çelik and Özdevecioğlu, 2001). In this context, the main focuses of the research were: determining the socio-demographic characteristics of women, the reasons for starting a business, the problems they face in starting and maintaining a business, and the tendency to organize. At the same time, the features that differentiate women entrepreneurs from male entrepreneurs have also been examined. It is stated that women entrepreneurs play different roles in the establishment stages of enterprises and are usually involved in the establishment of either small-scale enterprises or companies with little development opportunity (Kutanis, 2003). Moreover, it can be said that women entrepreneurs mostly operate in sectors related to the so-called informal economy (Nayır, 2008).

2.1. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Factors

Women want to start their own business for a variety of reasons. Entrepreneurship is considered as an alternative way for women to get rid of economic and social dependence. While economic needs have an impact on the decisions of women entrepreneurs, their motivation to have their own workplace and not wanting to work for wages and salaries are important factors that mobilize such entrepreneurs. Although entrepreneurship requires economic, social and psychological risks and long hours of work, the desire for economic independence leads individuals to start their own businesses. For some women, having a job is also seen as a way of integrating family obligations and working life and strengthening family relationships. Entrepreneurship should be considered as an empowering process for women regardless of the driving factors. In Turkey as well as other countries, since the 1980s women who seek to start businesses have been receiving encouragement and support from agencies on the challenges that they might face. Such support varies and could include special political intervention areas, bank loans provided to women entrepreneurs who established their first businesses, encouraging solidarity among women entrepreneurs, and projects

encouraging housewives to start their own businesses with small principal amounts. Such are the steps taken in this field so far.

The main motivation factors leading women to entrepreneurship can be listed as follows;

- Women's desire to realize their own business idea or an imaginary idea,
- Women's need to succeed,
- Women have a workplace or business inherited from the family or otherwise transferred,
- As a result of only one person working in the family, the difficulty of living on a person's income,
- Lack of paid employment opportunities for women or lack of other options for employment,
- Prioritizing men in employment in some business lines due to personal bias and misconduct,
- Profitability, better living, high social status and other such reasons.

2.2. Challenges of Women Entrepreneurs

It has been found in the results of the research that there are differences in the perception of the problems, leadership characteristics, performance of the enterprise, financial structure, and organizational culture of the enterprises that women have within the scope of entrepreneurship activities in economic life (Çelik and Özdevecioğlu, 2001). On the other hand, Watkins and Watkins (1984) concluded that men's entrepreneurship backgrounds and past experiences are more numerous than women's, and so women entrepreneurs are generally not prepared for the establishment of enterprises and therefore must assume more risk than men (Kutanis, 2003). In other words, it can be stated that women entrepreneurs have different motivations, skill levels, and professional backgrounds (Çelebi, 1997).

In this context, the problems faced by women in entrepreneurship activities can generally be divided into two groups. Among these, the problems under the title of being a woman can be listed as follows:

- traditional belief and pressure of the society that exists in patriarchal societies which considers that the place of the woman is the home and that a woman cannot take any initiative without the permission of a man (Güldal, 2006, Cam, 2003);
- gender-based role discrimination which is effective in determining which occupation or position is women's work and which is men's work (Örücü et al., 2007 :, Gökakın, 2000: 114);
- sexual and emotional harassment (Kocacık and Gökkaya, 2005, Çelik and Özdevecioğlu, 2001);
- the glass ceiling barrier that prevents women from rising in the organization (Anafarta et al., 2008);
- barriers arising from laws (Ecevit, 2007); distrust, lack of experience, and expectation of failure for women in business life (Toksöz, 2007, Davidsson, 1995);
- the problem posed by the role dilemma between private and working lives of female entrepreneurs (Narin et al., 2006, Özdevecioğlu and Aktaş, 2007: 6);
- low education level (Kansız and Acuner, 2008, Yetim, 2008);
- the role models that women entrepreneurs can take as an example from men counterparts (OECD, 2004; Davidsson, 1995; Delmar, 2000) and the lack of adequate capital for women to engage in entrepreneurial activities (OECD, 2004, Groot, 2001).

Another problem that women face in entrepreneurship activities can be grouped under the heading of problems arising from work and environmental conditions. These are; the lack of a holistic view of women's entrepreneurship worldwide and the inability to

organize, organizational diversity and coordination challenges, and barriers to policy development and implementation (Ecevit, 2007).

2.3. General Review of Women Entrepreneurs in Turkey

The UN declared “International Women’s Year” in 1975 to strengthen the status of women. Because of the impact of this declaration, in Turkey, the concept – indeed, the phenomenon – of women’s entrepreneurship emerged as a new liberal policy.

Parallel with many other countries in the world, in Turkey the strategies related to women's entrepreneurship are aimed at increasing employment for women, helping women be the boss of their own affairs, take risks, and play a role in the decision-making process, and encouraging women's innovation processes (Shepherd, 2006). It is envisaged to develop new policies and strategies and cooperate with all stakeholders in order to ensure equality between men and women, strengthen women's positions in all areas of social life, and prevent all forms of discrimination against women. For this purpose, the General Directorate of the Status of Women (KSSGM) was established in Turkey in 1990 under the Prime Ministry. This institution pointed out the necessity of increasing women's employment in order to elevate women’s social status, and supported research on women entrepreneurship. Another reason for the efforts to increase women's employment is that Turkey signed the “Convention on the Elimination of all forms of Discrimination Against Women [CEDAW]” (1985) and the Beijing Declaration (1995). These agreements impose the responsibility on governments for eliminating gender inequalities.

In order to support women's entrepreneurship, many organizations came into play and tried to create supply (funds, resources etc.) for women's entrepreneurship. Turkey Business Association General Manager, Small and Medium Enterprises Development and Support Administration (KOSGEB), T. C. Public institutions such as the Ministry of Family, and Social Policies were genuine leaders in this process. In the 2000s, the issue of women's employment was one of the special areas supported by the European Commission and was reflected in development plans (EC, 2002; 2004). Within the scope of the Eighth Five-Year Development Plan (2001-2005), a center was established by the KSSGM for the purpose of evaluating entrepreneurship and manual labor as well

as directing women to income generating activities. It is in fact planned to increase female employment through loan applications.

2.4. Women Entrepreneurs and Social Impact

Women's entrepreneurship is generally a special area of employment and women's employment. The studies on the labor force participation of women in Turkey has intensified since the 1980s. This interest in women's employment is closely related to export-oriented development strategies, especially in developing countries. The problems experienced in the import substitution policy of the developing countries led to a search for ways to integrate with the global market by using domestic resources and increased the load on labor-intensive sectors and women's labor in these sectors.

Today, entrepreneurship is seen as a key factor of economic growth and development due to its functions such as turning small savings into capital, bringing idle resources into the economy, increasing the productivity of labor, and preventing unemployment by creating new jobs. The projects aimed at supporting women entrepreneurs generally lead to goals such as economic development and growth, increasing women's participation in the labor market and reducing unemployment, increasing household welfare and combating poverty, empowering women, and ensuring gender equality. Therefore, while supporting entrepreneurship, it is expected that women will be able to play a more active role in the society's economic and social life. However, the support mechanisms that assume the female entrepreneur as a uniform and homogeneous group ignore the differences in socio-economic status of women.

3. Research Methodology

The main purpose of this qualitative study is to determine how women understand their social role model as a woman and a social agent. As the qualitative research method is seen as the best approach in terms of gathering information via the close connection between researcher and participant, it was decided that conducting semi-structured interviews may help to reach the objective of the study.

Through using well-defined, open-ended, or leading questions, the researcher can study multiple cases of women entrepreneurs and leading factors like age, education level,

marital status, and entire work experience – all factors which might affect entrepreneurial activity in a positive or negative way. The targeted respondents might indeed be different from one another in terms of their past experience or, for example, in “meaning making” or “decision making” when the real situation requires purposeful action at that moment. It seems that internal and external factors exert a significant effect on the performance of the entrepreneurs. Therefore, implementing interview-based data collection could be a proper method to obtain the opinions and attitudes of the participants (Orcher, 2005).

3.1. Population and Sampling

The population of this study are women social entrepreneurs. We targeted the well-known international social organization Ashoka and its female members who work as social initiators. This study is planning to reach some of the women who are actively working in education, contributing to the economic development, social justice, and environmental development of Turkey. However, the women who conduct their duties in Istanbul are the primary group to be considered in this research.

The “purposive sampling” is the most appropriate sampling method for this study as it is the method that meets the criteria of the researcher. Moreover, the purposive sampling method is the best method in research in which limited numbers of people can be served as the primary data sources of the conducted research. Use of this method enables the generalization of overall results according to the collected data from the focused population.

The suitable candidates were selected from their profiles which are uploaded to their organization’s websites. Also, in the candidate choosing process, their entrepreneurial carrier and their social impact level are taken into consideration. Organizations such as Ashoka intensively support the most leading and innovative social entrepreneurs and are able to provide a list of women based on areas of interest and working place. Therefore, an alternative step was searching Ashoka's women entrepreneurs’ profile on social networks and asking women to participate in the interview.

12 women were targeted to be invited for the research interview. One of them was not an Ashoka's fellow. She has been awarded by the prize of the best social entrepreneur of

the 2018 year that sponsored by Garanti Bank in Turkey's Social Woman Entrepreneur Competition. It was decided to take this opportunity and to invite her for the interview. The women of this research work tirelessly to improve social welfare in different areas. They are active in many different areas such as empowering women, protecting the environment, paving the way for young people and guiding them on the right path. Subsequently, the purpose of the study was to explore upon collected results from the interview their entrepreneurial story and to reveal individual merit in terms of possible threats on the career path.

3.2. Interview Process and Analysis Method

The data which constitute the basis of the analysis was derived from the planned interviews. Data collection were conducted with each participant through face-to-face interviews, audio recording and note taking. According to Ehrich (2005), using text format for describing the discussion in the interview is naturally interconnected with gaining information and an observation of the individual's experiences. Such data are transcribed into a typed format. The audio recorder has assured the accuracy of the information that was interpreted from the candidate's own words.

In the first part of the study, the information about the demographic traits of the interviewed entrepreneur women was determined and the gathered information was given below in Table 1:

Table 1. Demographic Traits of Entrepreneurial Women in Research

PARTICIPATION NUMBER	FELLOWSHIP YEAR	DEMOGRAPHIC TRAITS
1	2000	Age: 64 Education: Bachelor Marital Status: Single Children: 2
2	2003	Age: 48 Education: Bachelor Marital Status: Single Children: None
3	The best social woman entrepreneur of the 2018 year	Age: 35 Education: Master Marital Status: Single Children: None
4	2006	Age: 46 Education: High School Marital Status: Married Children: 2
5	2007	Age: 59 Education: Bachelor Marital Status: Single (Widow) Children: 2
6	2012	Age: 37 Education: Bachelor Marital Status: Married Children: 2
7	2013	Age: 43 Education: Master Marital Status: Married Children: 2
8	2006	Age: 64 Education: Bachelor Marital Status: Single (Divorced) Children: 2
9	2014	Age: 43 Education: PHD Marital Status: Single (Divorced) Children: 1
10	2001	Age: 68 Education: PHD Marital Status: Single (Divorced) Children: 2
11	2015	Age: 52 Education: Bachelor Marital Status: Married Children: 1
12	2014	Age: 45 Education: Master Marital Status: Single Children: None

According to details included in Table 1, women who were taking part in this research are comparably different from each other with age group, education level and working experience and etc. In the next stages of the research, it will be revealed the proportion of the effect of demographic data on their business life.

Table 2. Intrinsic and Extrinsic Motivation Factors

PARTISIPANTS	INTRINSIC MOTIVATION	EXTRINSIC MOTIVATION
PARTICIPANT 1	Empowerment of women, welfare and happiness of others	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 2	Nature and sensitivity towards to environment	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 3	Change and improvement of girls	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 4	Empowerment of youngsters	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 5	Positive changes of the women and children	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 6	Keeping people being motivated and to follow own dreams	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 7	Making a ground for positive change and creating social value	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 8	Self-realization through believing in own strengths and contribute to society	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 9	To encourage people to take place in social welfare	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 10	Meeting needs in society with the gained knowledge and experiences	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 11	Being a reason for the positive changes	not mentioned
PARTICIPANT 12	Passion to work and added value by own efforts	not mentioned

Factors driving women to entrepreneurship are intrinsic (be independent, self-realization, being successful etc.) and extrinsic (family support, economic independence, legal, political and administrative factors) were concerned in the concept of the research. The impulse that motivates an individual to act may be both, intrinsic and extrinsic motivators. Intrinsic motivation is to stably go on while we are satisfied with the activity that we are responsible for. Business becomes pleasure in this term. Motivation is the force that directs and activates behavior. Thus, it inspires people to move on towards a specific purpose and determines the direction of their movement, their thoughts, hopes, beliefs, in short, desire, need or fears.

The women in this research were inspired by intrinsic motivators. These results are the main reason for fulfilling social business. As per the results in Table 2, it is clearly seen that they are highly satisfied to be part of the positive changes.

Table 3. Major Challenges of Women

PARTICIPANTS	Lack of required education	A need for family support	Being a woman	Reliable social network	Managing work-life balance	Prejudice towards women strength	Challenge in finding financial support	Lack of leadership skills
PARTICIPANT 1		✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓	✓
PARTICIPANT 2	✓	✓		✓	✓	✓		✓
PARTICIPANT 3	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓		✓
PARTICIPANT 4		✓	✓	✓		✓		✓
PARTICIPANT 5		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
PARTICIPANT 6		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
PARTICIPANT 7		✓		✓	✓		✓	✓
PARTICIPANT 8		✓		✓	✓	✓	✓	
PARTICIPANT 9		✓		✓	✓			✓
PARTICIPANT 10		✓					✓	✓
PARTICIPANT 11		✓	✓	✓	✓		✓	✓
PARTICIPANT 12		✓		✓		✓	✓	

As can be seen from Table 3, the women, who were the subject of the research, have faced several major difficulties during their entrepreneurship activity. A need for family support, the building of a reliable social network, difficulty in managing work-life balance, the challenge in finding financial support and lack of leadership skills are the ones that are more heavily mentioned in the answers of social entrepreneurs. Each woman has interpreted how these challenges affect their business lives differently. Thus, answers of the respondents are interpreted upon directly conveying the opinions of the people on the basis of the answers that can be considered as examples.

CONCLUSION

Social entrepreneurship consists of sociality and entrepreneurship, which seem to be two opposing concepts. The sociality of the concept can be explained by the fact that social entrepreneurship deals with social problems, is established for a social purpose and the field of activity is the social sector. Entrepreneurship adds value to the application of innovative and creative methods with determination. The most important factor for social entrepreneurship is to create social change. Making a profit is an opportunity for sustainability and making new social investments.

It is argued that social entrepreneurship reduces social problems and stimulates transformation. What all social entrepreneurship definitions have in common is that organizations that have a social mission, not for a commercial purpose, see

opportunities to create social impacts and create a long-term impact on society through innovative means.

Generally, the marginalization of women in the eyes of society leads to their consignment to subordinate positions (Harding, 2004). This might be utilized to clarify why they are underexplored in business hypothesis and practice (Ahl, 2006).

In terms of understanding women entrepreneurship, the initial step was to comprehend the inspirations that drive the enterprising movement. Current research thus aims to find out the targeted women's derived motivational factors that lead them on the way to the ultimate goal. In parallel, it is assumed to reveal the possible constraints faced by women in which they are implementing constructive solutions. With the end goal of this study, the social collaboration that women are situated in – as woman and social entrepreneur – helps shape their insight and connection with themselves as well as other people (Griffin, 2003).

Women social entrepreneurs have a place with at any rate two social groups - women and social entrepreneurs with a longing to have a social effect. In this manner, their perspectives on the world are likely impacted by both of these features.

In the entrepreneurship literature experts accepted that by centering upon both the more dominant social innovative position and the less powerful social position as a woman, the impact of the women had the option to offer a wider, deeper comprehension of women, social entrepreneurs, as far as how they make and experience their surrounding world and what this implies about their various characters.

According to the results of the interview data within the scope of the research object, social women entrepreneurs are mostly acting with the guidance of internal factors. Social activities are not planned in advance, it is in line with the energy or feelings that a person has inside. Making a ground for the changes or triggering these changes are inspiring women to pursue own goals. The change in individuals' perception of a social problem is made through long and difficult struggles and via mutual interaction.

The women who participated in the study evaluated the difficulties encountered in entrepreneurship activities from different perspectives. Challenges were displayed

according to voice recordings: a building of a reliable social network, difficulty in managing work-life balance, the challenge in finding financial support and lack of leadership skills are the most mentioned factors. Surprisingly, as per the results, of the research, women have not encountered the difficulties of being a woman. As per some women's conclusion, it was related to a new concept of social entrepreneurship and people's responses to entrepreneurship activities, not women's identities in this context.

In conclusion, individuals of this research are the women who struggle to challenges with intrinsically motivating factors. Regardless of the issue, they are moving on with limitless enthusiasm for providing sustainable solutions. Their passion for entrepreneurial activity is guiding them throughout the business life. In this context, the study is putting light on women's business experience and it is expected to contribute to other future studies.

REFERENCES

Anafarta, N, Sarvan, F., &Yapici, N. (2008), Konaklama İşletmelerinde Kadın Yöneticilerin Cam Tavan Algısı: Antalya İlinde Bir Araştırma, *Akdeniz İ.İ.B.F. Dergisi*, 15,111-137.

- Austin, J., Steenson, H., & Wei-Ekillern, J. (2006). Social and Commercial Entrepreneurship: Same, Different, Or Both? *Entrepreneurship Theory and Practice*, 1-22.
- Aytaç, Ö. (2006). Girişimcilik: Sosyo-Kültürel bir Perspektif. *Dumlupınar Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Dergisi*, 15, 139-160.
- Cin, H., & Günay, G. (2013). Girişimcilerin Girişimcilik Tipleri ile Duygusal Zekaları Arasındaki İlişki: Edirne Örneği. *Girişimcilik ve Kalkınma Dergisi*, 8(2), 7-32.
- Çelebi, N. (1997). *Turizm Sektöründeki Küçük İşyeri ve Örgütlerinde Kadın Girişimciler*, Ankara: T.C. Başbakanlık Kadının Statüsü ve Sorunları Genel Müdürlüğü,
- Çelik, C., & Özdevecioğlu, M. (2001). Kadın Girişimcilerin Demografik Özellikleri ve Karşılaştıkları sorunlara İlişkin Nevşehir İlinde Bir Araştırma”, 1. Orta Anadolu Kongresi, Nevşehir, 487-498.
- Çevik, E. (2006). *Girişimcilerin, Girişimcilik Tipleri ile Çalışma Amaçları Arasındaki İlişki*. İstanbul: Marmara Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Dees, J. (1998). The Meaning of Social Entrepreneurship. *The Kauffman Center for Entrepreneurial Leadership*.
- Dinç, A. (2001). İktisadi Düşünce Tarihinde Girişimcilik Kavramı Üzerine Notlar. *İstanbul Üniversitesi Siyasal Bilgiler Fakültesi Dergisi*, 23-24.
- Döm, S. (2008). *Girişimcilik ve Küçük İşletme Yöneticiliği*. Ankara: Detay Yayıncılık.
- Ecevit, Y. (2007). *Türkiye’de Kadın Girişimciliğine Eleştirel Bir Yaklaşım*, 1. Baskı, Ankara: Uluslararası Çalışma Ofisi (ILO).
- Güler, B.K. (2008). *Sosyal Girişimcilik*, Ankara: Efil Yayınevi.
- Hitt, M., Ireland, R. C., & Sexton, D. (2001). Guest Editor's Introduction to the Special Issue: Strategic Entrepreneurship: Entrepreneurial Strategies for Wealth Creation. *Strategic Management Journal*, 22(6/7), 479-491.

- Ireland, R., Hitt, M., & Sirmon, D. (2003). A Model of Strategic Entrepreneurship: The Construct and Its Dimensions. *Journal of Management*, 29(6), 963-989.
- Kocacik, F., & Gökçaya V.B. (2005), "Türkiye'de Çalışan Kadınlar Ve Sorunları," *C.Ü.İ.İ.B.F. Dergisi*, 6 (1), 195-219.
- Kutunis, R. Ö. (2003). Girişimcilikte Cinsiyet Faktörü: Kadın Girişimciler, 11. Yönetim ve Organizasyon Kongresi Bildiriler Kitabı, Afyon.
- Narin, M., Marşap, A., & Gürol, M.A. (2006). Global Kadın Girişimciliğinin Maksimizasyonunu Hedefleme: Uluslararası Arenada Örgütlenme Ve Ağ Oluşturma, *Gazi Üniversitesi İ.İ.B.F. Dergisi*, 8 (1), 65-78.
- Nayır D. Z. (2008). İşi ve Ailesi Arasındaki Kadın: Tekstil ve Bilgi İşlem Girişimcilerinin Rol Çatışmasına Getirdikleri Çözüm Stratejileri, *Ege Akademik Bakış*, 8 (2), 631-650.
- Örücü, E., Kiliç R., & Kiliç T. (2007), Cam Tavan Sendromu ve Kadınların Üst Düzey Yönetici Pozisyonuna Yükselmelerindeki Engeller: Balıkesir İli Örneği, *Celal Bayar Üniversitesi İ.İ.B.F. Yönetim ve Ekonomi Dergisi*, 14 (2), 117-135.
- Paksoy, S., & Aydoğdu, M. (2010). Bölgesel Kalkınmada Girişimciliğin Geliştirilmesi: GAP-GİDEM Örnekleri. *Girişimcilik ve Kalkınma Dergisi*, 5(1), 113-134.
- Scarborough, N. (2011). *Essential of Entrepreneurship*. New-York: Prentice Hall.
- Sciascia, S., & De Vita, R. (2004). The Development of Entrepreneurship Research. *Liuc Papers No: 146*, Serie Economia Aziendale 19.
- Sobel, S. R. (2013, 01 02). Entrepreneurship. 09 20, 2019 tarihinde econlib.org adresinden alındı
- Spear, R. (2006). Social Entrepreneurship: A Different Model? *International Journal of Social Economics*, 33 (5), 399-410.
- Tekin, M. (2005). *Hayallerin Gerçeğe Dönüşümü: Girişimcilik*. Konya: Damla Ofset Matbaası.

- Thompson, J. (2002). The World of the Social Entrepreneurship. *The International Journal of Public Sector Management*, 412-431.
- Toksöz, G. (2007). İşgücü Piyasasının Toplumsal Cinsiyet Perspektifinden Analizi ve Bölgeler Arası Dengesizlikler, *Çalışma ve Toplum*, 4.
- Top, S. (2006). *Girişimcilik Keşif Süreci*, İstanbul: Beta Basım Yayın Dağıtım.
- Tokgöz, e. (2001). *Türkiye'nin İktisadi Gelişme Tarihi (1914-2001)*, Ankara: İmaj Yayınevi.
- Tosunoğlu, B. T. (2003). *Girişimcilik ve Türkiye'nin Ekonomik Gelişme Sürecinde Türkiye'nin Yeri*. Eskişehir: Eskişehir Anadolu Üniversitesi Sosyal Bilimler Enstitüsü.
- Weerawardena, J., & Mort, G. (2006). Investigating Social Entrepreneurship: A Multi-Dimensional Model. *Journal of World Business*, 21-35.